

Career Management and Performance of Commercial Banks in Rivers State

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This study investigates the relationship between career management and organizational performance of commercial banks in Rivers State. The study specifically evaluates how career advancement and performance evaluation as dimensions of career management relate to productivity and operational efficiency. The research adopted a quantitative design and utilized Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS version 4.0 to analyze the data. Results reveal that both career advancement and performance evaluation significantly influence productivity and operational efficiency. Recommendations are offered to improve structured career management practices in the banking sector. Banks should create clear, transparent career advancement paths to motivate employees and drive productivity

Keywords: Career Management, Career Advancement, Performance Evaluation, Productivity, Operational Efficiency, Commercial Banks

INTRODUCTION

In today's dynamic and competitive business environment, career management has become a vital element in enhancing employee commitment and performance. Career management encompasses a set of processes including career planning, development, mentoring, performance evaluation, and career advancement opportunities aimed at aligning individual career goals with organizational objectives (Baruch, 2004). Commercial banks, as key drivers of economic development, depend significantly on the commitment and performance of their employees to achieve operational efficiency and productivity.

In the Nigerian banking sector, increased customer expectations, digital transformation, and regulatory shifts have made it imperative for banks to maximize employee performance. This can only be achieved when banks strategically manage the careers of their workforce, ensuring opportunities for career advancement and providing regular performance evaluations (Egbu et al.,

2021). Employees who perceive growth opportunities within their organization are more likely to stay motivated, productive, and aligned with the organization's vision (Noe, 2017).

Despite its importance, career management is often overlooked in many organizations, or only practiced in a fragmented manner. This has led to low productivity, high turnover rates, and decreased operational efficiency. Therefore, it becomes pertinent to examine how career management strategies such as career advancement and performance evaluation impact the performance of commercial banks in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Although career management has been widely recognized as a strategic human resource tool for enhancing employee and organizational performance, its practical implementation within commercial banks in Rivers State appears to be inconsistent and under-researched. Several banks lack structured policies to support employee career advancement, and performance evaluations are often perceived as biased or infrequent,

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leading to dissatisfaction among employees (Okorie & Basse, 2020). The inability of banks to adequately manage careers results in reduced employee morale, lack of motivation, poor succession planning, and ultimately diminished organizational productivity and operational efficiency. Moreover, while various studies have focused on general human resource practices and organizational performance, few have critically examined the specific relationship between career management practices—particularly career advancement and performance evaluation—and key performance indicators such as productivity and operational efficiency in the banking sector of Rivers State.

Hence, this study seeks to bridge this gap by investigating the relationship between career management and organizational performance of commercial banks, with specific emphasis on career advancement, performance evaluation, productivity, and operational efficiency.

Research Objectives

The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Examine the relationship between career advancement and productivity of commercial banks in Rivers State.
2. Examine the relationship between career advancement and operational efficiency of commercial banks in Rivers State.
3. Examine the relationship between performance evaluation and productivity of commercial banks in Rivers State.
4. Examine the relationship between performance evaluation and operational efficiency of commercial banks in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between career advancement and productivity of commercial banks in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between career advancement and operational efficiency of commercial banks in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between performance evaluation and productivity of commercial banks in Rivers State?
4. What is the relationship between performance evaluation and operational efficiency of commercial banks in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between career advancement and productivity of commercial banks in Rivers State.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between career

advancement and operational efficiency of commercial banks in Rivers State.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between performance evaluation and productivity of commercial banks in Rivers State.

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between performance evaluation and operational efficiency of commercial banks in Rivers State.

Review of Literature

This study is anchored on the Human Capital Theory and the Goal-Setting Theory. Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1964): This theory posits that investments in employee training, education, and career development increase the productivity and efficiency of individuals. It implies that organizations that invest in structured career management systems—such as career advancement opportunities and performance evaluations—are likely to enhance the performance of their workforce. Goal-Setting Theory (Locke & Latham, 1990): This theory emphasizes that clear, specific, and challenging goals lead to higher performance. Performance evaluation aligns with this theory, as it involves setting performance benchmarks and providing feedback that motivates employees to improve their output. By combining these theories, this study provides a solid foundation for understanding how career management practices can significantly influence the productivity and operational efficiency of commercial banks.

Concept of Career Management

Career management refers to the structured approach organizations use to assist employees in planning and managing their professional development (Greenhaus et al., 2010). It involves aligning employee aspirations with organizational goals through various mechanisms such as coaching, mentoring, succession planning, and training (Baruch, 2004). Career management is the lifelong process of managing learning, work, leisure, and transitions in order to move toward a personally determined and evolving preferred future (Armstrong, 2009). Career management is defined as “an ongoing, formalized effort by an organisation that focuses on developing and enriching the organisation’s human resources in the light of both the employees’ and the organisation’s needs” (Byars & Rue, 2014). McDougall and Vaughn (2017) argue that “Career management involves aligning individual subjective and more objective career aspects of an organisation to find a match between individual and organisational needs, personal characteristics and career roles.” This author views career management as a mutual role, based on the needs and circumstances of both individuals and organisations. Development involves preparing

employees for higher responsibilities in future. Effective career management results in increased employee engagement and contributes to improved organizational performance (Aguinis, 2009).

Career Advancement

Career advancement involves opportunities for upward mobility within the organization. It includes promotions, new responsibilities, and increased remuneration or job status (Arthur & Rousseau, 1996). Career advancement fosters employee motivation and has been linked to higher levels of productivity and operational output (Tella & Popoola, 2007). Employees who perceive potential for growth tend to put in more effort and align themselves with organizational objectives. Career advancement, according to (Naw et al. 2023), encompasses upward progression within an organisation, leading to higher positions or increased responsibilities. It involves strategic management of individual growth and learning, benefiting employees and organisations. Career advancement programs aid in leveraging internal resources effectively, and matching individuals' abilities and goals with organisational needs to enhance staffing and promotion practices. Such initiatives also facilitate smoother transitions between roles and increase workforce mobility, ultimately contributing to organisational productivity and performance while reducing turnover.

Performance Evaluation

Performance evaluation is a systematic process of assessing employee job performance against predetermined standards or expectations. It helps in identifying strengths and development needs, ensuring fairness in promotions, and facilitating communication between employees and management (DeNisi & Williams, 2018). When effectively implemented, performance evaluations boost employee confidence, accountability, and productivity (Pulakos, 2009). Performance evaluation, also known as performance review or appraisal, is a critical tool for assessing individual, group, or organisational performance, identifying areas for improvement, and guiding resource allocation and program enhancement (Gong et al. 2021)

Concept of Performance

Organizational performance refers to how well an organization achieves its objectives in terms of productivity, efficiency, profitability, and customer satisfaction (Richard et al., 2009). In this study, performance is assessed through productivity and operational efficiency. Performance, based on Brumbach (2008), encompasses both actions and results since the performer's actions convert an intangible idea into a

tangible action. He sees it as more than just common tools for accomplishing goals; rather, he sees it as behavior that are the product of the psychological and physiological work required to complete activities and that can be assessed without reference to results.

Productivity

Productivity is the output of employees or departments relative to the input or resources utilized. It is a critical metric in banking performance, reflecting how well employees convert organizational resources into financial results or services (Huselid, 1995). It is believed that the more disparate the objectives of the various people, organizations, and entities involved in the issue of productivity, the more disparate their notions of productivity will be (Mankins, 2017).

Operational Efficiency

Operational efficiency refers to an organization's ability to deliver services in a cost-effective manner without compromising quality. In commercial banks, this includes efficient processing of transactions, customer service turnaround times, and effective use of technology (Yamoah, 2014). Operational efficiency, according to Kalluru & Bhat (2009), is the ability of a company to reduce undesirables and increase asset capacities in order to provide customers with high-quality goods and services. Among many other things, efficient and competent professionals, genuine innovation, proper acquisition execution, business return to scale, and supply chain management are all essential to an organization's operational efficiency.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Several studies have investigated the influence of career management on organizational outcomes. For instance, Oki and Ogbari (2021) found a significant positive relationship between career advancement opportunities and employee productivity in Nigerian commercial banks. Similarly, Udu and Anazodo (2019) observed that structured performance evaluations enhanced operational efficiency in the banking sector by promoting accountability and goal clarity.

Johnson and Akinwale (2020) reported that career advancement opportunities such as promotions and skill development positively influenced productivity levels in the banking industry. Olaniyan and Okemakinde (2018) suggest that career advancement pathways contribute significantly to improving internal processes and customer responsiveness, indicating higher operational efficiency.

Adewale and Osagie (2017) emphasized that performance evaluation, when linked with employee

Table 1: Reliability Test

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha
Career Advancement	0.711
Operational Efficiency	0.783
Performance Evaluation	0.749
Productivity	0.767

Table 2: Validity Test

	AVE	Career Advancement	Operational Efficiency	Performance Evaluation	Productivity
Career Advancement	0.632	0.795			
Operational Efficiency	0.556	0.395	0.746		
Performance Evaluation	0.520	0.492	0.225	0.721	
Productivity	0.600	0.320	0.264	0.295	0.749

Table 3: Hypotheses Testing Result

Hypotheses	Path Relationship	β	p-value	R ²	Decision
Ho ₁	Career advancement → Productivity	0.611	0.000	0.723	Reject null hypothesis
Ho ₂	Career advancement → Operational Efficiency	0.569	0.001	0.695	Reject null hypothesis
Ho ₃	Performance Evaluation → Productivity	0.533	0.002	0.688	Reject null hypothesis
Ho ₄	Performance Evaluation → Operational Efficiency	0.507	0.003	0.672	Reject null hypothesis

feedback and development plans, led to marked improvements in productivity metrics. Eke and Nwachukwu (2020) highlighted that structured performance appraisal systems contributed to optimized resource usage and streamlined operations, thereby enhancing operational efficiency.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative research design using a survey method. The target population comprised employees of selected commercial banks in Rivers State. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data. Stratified sampling was applied to ensure adequate representation across job roles. Data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) through SmartPLS version 4.0. This method allowed for the assessment of measurement and structural models simultaneously, offering robust estimates for path coefficients and validity measures.

All constructs met the reliability thresholds with Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values above 0.70, indicating high internal consistency. All constructs achieved Average Variance Extracted (AVE) above 0.5, signifying convergent validity. Diagonal values (bold) are higher than off-diagonal values, indicating discriminant validity.

Analysis and Discussion

The study administered 238 questionnaires, of which 201 were successfully retrieved and analyzed, indicating a retrieval rate of 90.5%.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Career advancement significantly enhances productivity. Growth opportunities such as promotions, skill-development programs, or leadership roles foster a sense of purpose and belonging. Employees become more engaged and invest their energy and time into delivering higher-quality work. Additionally, the findings suggest that empowered employees are more likely to collaborate effectively, achieve personal goals, and align their efforts with organizational objectives, resulting in measurable productivity gains. This supports the view that growth opportunities encourage higher output among employees (Johnson & Akinwale, 2020).

Career advancement also leads to greater operational efficiency. As employees ascend into higher positions, they often acquire leadership skills that strengthen team coordination and ensure the optimal utilization of resources. Clarity in career progression also reduces uncertainties about roles and responsibilities, enabling departments to collaborate effectively without overlaps.

Organizations that establish well-defined career advancement plans achieve better alignment between their workforce and strategic objectives, ultimately leading to cost reductions, faster processes, and operational excellence. Structured career progression ensures clarity in roles and effective resource use (Olaniyan & Okemakinde, 2018).

Performance evaluation positively affects productivity. For employees, receiving actionable feedback fosters self-awareness and drives personal development, while constructive criticism highlights opportunities for skill enhancement. Additionally, the regularity of performance reviews ensures that employees remain aligned with organizational expectations, reducing errors and increasing output quality. For managers, evaluations offer a strategic tool to identify high performers, address underperformance, and allocate resources efficiently. Performance reviews also foster collaboration between employees and supervisors, creating a supportive environment that boosts morale and productivity. Feedback systems drive improvement and accountability (Adewale & Osagie, 2017).

Performance evaluation significantly influences operational efficiency. By defining clear benchmarks and metrics for success, organizations ensure that employees focus their efforts on high-priority tasks. Evaluations also promote accountability, encouraging employees to take ownership of their contributions. Moreover, by identifying skill gaps and addressing them through targeted training, organizations reduce inefficiencies and create a more capable workforce. This process ultimately leads to better resource allocation, reduced operational bottlenecks, and adaptability to changing business demands. Operational efficiency benefits from performance evaluation practices that align individual goals with organizational strategy (Eke & Nwachukwu, 2020).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study confirms that career management dimensions—career advancement and performance evaluation—significantly influence productivity and operational efficiency in commercial banks within Rivers State. Effective implementation of these practices is crucial for sustaining competitive advantage and organizational success. Career management directly influences productivity by enhancing employee capabilities and morale. Career management enhances operational efficiency by ensuring that the right people are in the right roles with the right skills. The following recommendations were put forward.

- i. Banks should create clear, transparent career advancement paths to motivate employees and drive productivity.
- ii. Commercial institutions should incorporate career

advancement structures in their strategic planning to foster operational improvements.

- iii. Banks should develop standardized performance evaluation systems that focus on continuous feedback and employee development.
- iv. Commercial banks should align performance metrics with operational goals to ensure evaluation systems contribute directly to efficiency gains.

REFERENCES

- Adewale, A., & Osagie, R. (2017). Influence of performance appraisal on employee productivity in Nigerian banks. *J. Human Res. Manage.* 5(2), 47–55.
- Aguinis, H. (2013). *Performance management*. Pearson Education.
- Armstrong, M., & Taylor, S. (2020). *Armstrong's handbook of human resource management practice* (15th ed.). Kogan Page Publishers.
- Becker, G. S. (1964). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education*. University of Chicago Press.
- Drucker, P. F. (2007). *The effective executive: The definitive guide to getting the right things done*. Harper Business.
- Eke, N. N., & Nwachukwu, C. C. (2020). Performance evaluation and operational efficiency in the Nigerian banking sector. *Int. J. Bus. Soc. Sci.* 11(1), 55–65.
- Greenhaus, J. H., Callanan, G. A., & Godshalk, V. M. (2010). *Career management* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Johnson, I. J., & Akinwale, A. A. (2020). Career advancement and employee productivity in Nigeria's financial institutions. *Nig. J. Manage. Res.* 15(3):101–115.
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2002). Building a practically useful theory of goal setting and task motivation: A 35-year odyssey. *American Psychol.* 57(9), 705–717.
- Noe, R. A. (2013). *Employee training and development* (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Olaniyan, D. A., & Okemakinde, T. (2018). Career advancement as a predictor of organizational efficiency in Nigeria's banking sector. *J. Econ. and Sustainable Develop.* 9(17), 34–40.
- Oki, M. I., & Ogbari, M. E. (2021). Career development strategies and organizational performance in the Nigerian banking industry. *Global J. Manage. and Bus. Res.* 21(5): 14–25.
- Udu, A. A., & Anazodo, R. O. (2019). Performance appraisal and employee effectiveness in Nigerian deposit money banks. *Manage. Stud. and Econ. Syst.* 4(1): 35–44.
- Aguinis, H. (2009). *Performance management* (2nd ed.). Pearson Education.
- Arthur, M. B., & Rousseau, D. M. (1996). *The boundaryless career: A new employment principle for a new organizational era*. Oxford University Press.
- Baruch, Y. (2004). *Transforming careers: From linear to multidirectional career paths*. *Career Development International*, 9(1), 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13620430410518147>
- Becker, G. S. (1964). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education*. University of Chicago Press.
- DeNisi, A. S., & Williams, K. J. (2018). Appraisal performance. In *APA Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*.
- Egbu, G. E., Uche, I. B., & Chukwu, A. (2021). Human resource practices and employee performance in Nigerian banks. *Int. J. Manage. Res.* 9(2), 45–58.
- Greenhaus, J. H., Callanan, G. A., & Godshalk, V. M. (2010). *Career management* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Huselid, M. A. (1995). The impact of human resource management practices on turnover, productivity, and corporate financial performance. *Acad. Manage. J.* 38(3), 635–672.
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (1990). *A theory of goal setting & task performance*. Prentice Hall.

- Noe, R. A. (2017). *Employee training and development* (7th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Okorie, N., & Basse, S. (2020). Career development and employee retention in Nigerian banks. *Nig. J. Bus. Manage.* 14(1), 72–83.
- Pulakos, E. D. (2009). *Performance management: A new approach for driving business results*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Richard, P. J., Devinney, T. M., Yip, G. S., & Johnson, G. (2009). Measuring organizational performance: Towards methodological best practice. *Journal of Management*, 35(3), 718– 804.
- Tella, A., & Popoola, S. O. (2007). Work motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment of library personnel in academic and research libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1–16.
- Yamoah, E. E. (2014). The link between human resource capacity building and job performance. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(3), 139–150.